

**THE MUSIC OF REASON, THE REASON FOR MUSIC:
MATHEMATICS AT THE SERVICE
OF COMPOSITION PRACTICE AND AESTHETICS**

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Summary

**The Music of Reason, the Reason for Music:
Mathematics at the Service of Composition Practice and Aesthetics**

The relationship between composition and mathematics is long-standing, broad and multifaceted and crosses several topics and disciplines. In this context, the aim of this research is to offer a brief insight on how mathematics have been and could be used explicitly and willingly in the specific field of music composition, serving and nourish the artistic practice as a useful and reliable option that can lead to unique findings, outputs and aesthetics at different levels. In this regard, it is shown and discussed how mathematics can be a powerful tool that is useful for composers not only for studying musical elements, for shaping them and for solving specific musical issues, but even as a means for unique aesthetic aims and as an actual peculiar instrument that can potentially trigger new musical ideas. Illustrative examples are then given from the techniques and aesthetics of different notable composer within the framework of Western art music culture, along with instances from the Author's composition practice.

Key words: Composition, Mathematics, Aesthetics, Artistic Research.

Rezumat

**Muzica rațiunii, rațiunea muzicii:
matematica în serviciul practicii componistice și esteticii**

Relația dintre compoziția muzicală și matematică are rădăcini adânci, este complexă și polivalentă și angrenează mai multe subiecte și discipline. În acest context, scopul cercetării de față este de a oferi o analiză expresă a modului în care matematica a fost și ar putea fi utilizată eficient în domeniul specific al compoziției muzicale. Matematica e în stare să servească nevoilor practicii artistice, să devină o opțiune utilă capabilă să genereze descoperiri, rezultate și orizonturi neașteptate. Autorul dezbate strategiile prin care matematica se transformă într-un instrument necesar pentru compozitorul, care va apela nu doar pentru articularea elementelor muzicale sau pentru soluționarea problemelor muzicale specifice, ci chiar pentru atingerea unor scopuri estetice majore, pentru accederea către deschideri conceptuale noi. Autorul își fortifică argumentele cu exemple din creația unor compozitori reprezentativi din cultura muzicală occidentală, precum și cu exemple din propria creație.

Cuvinte-cheie: compoziție, matematică, estetică, cercetare artistică.

Music and mathematics have been intertwined in Western culture from their very origins and have moved forward together for centuries. In fact, «music and mathematics have been bounded for more than two thousand years – from Pythagorean metaphysics to computer science, throughout medieval *quadrivium*, tuning [...] and organological issues, acoustics [...], systematic musicology and mathematical music theory [...], mathematically informed systems, aesthetics and treatises of music composition [...], etc. -, but only in the last few decades a specific research field has risen, [...]. It studies music with tools, methods and approaches explicitly derived

from mathematics and it saw the birth of conferences, journals, publications and academic events and positions specifically devoted to the topic» [5, p. 1813]. It should come then as no surprise that also the most preliminary and «basic dictionary of music relies on a mathematical terminology: durations are expressed by fractions, scale degrees by ordinals, intervals by cardinal numbers, etc.» [5, p. 1813]. Moreover, several traditional treatises of music theory and harmony often relies on mathematical concepts, tools and ideas.

Therefore, the relationship between composition and mathematics is indeed broad and multifaceted. For this reason, this research aims

at offering an insight on a narrowed down topic, trying to answer the following question: how has mathematics been and could be used explicitly and willingly in the specific field of music composition, serving and nourishing the artistic practice? So, the focus is on mathematics *for* composition, rather than on mathematics *in* composition. Such a focus might also overcome some aspects of the historical dichotomy between music theory and music practice, in which the metaphysical aspects and sides of mathematics had played a significant role.

In this regard, four different approaches have been identified: 1) mathematics for a more detailed insight of the musical elements involved in composition, namely mathematical music theory at the service of a preliminary knowledge for composition; 2) mathematical elements as powerful tools at the service of practical musical aims, issues and techniques in music composition; 3) mathematics as a unique trigger for original musical ideas; and 4) mathematically informed aesthetics of music composition. Although they are all to a certain extent linked, they will be briefly presented separately in the following four chapters.

1. Bodies of Discovery: Mathematics for Studying Musical Elements

As a matter of fact, mathematics is the most valid tool to give clear and reliable definitions, to undoubtedly prove properties and results of the so defined objects, to study their relations from an abstract point of view and to enumerate them. It is no coincidence that it is based on logic and it is one of the main tools of science¹. In fact, Charles Darwin even stated that «every new body of discovery is mathematical in form, because there is no other guidance we can have» [12, p. 540].

To give a preliminary example of the (sometimes unexploited) potential power of mathematics in investigating musical elements with compositional purposes, let us start with a historical case. In [17], Olivier Messiaen introduced the concept of modes with limited transpositions – *modes à*

1 The origin of the world ‘mathematics’ itself embodies the meaning of universal knowledge, as it comes from the old greek μάθημα, *máthēma*, that means ‘knowledge’, ‘study’, and even ‘learning’. Furthermore, recent studies have tried to mathematically model the creative process, with an emphasis on music composition. See for instance [8].

transpositions limitées –, i.e. modes which remain invariant under certain interval transpositions. For instance, a hexatonic scale is a trivial example. They played a fundamental role in his own musical language, being the harmonic framework of several of his compositions. But, as Guerino Mazzola pointed out, «Messiaen’s list includes seven modes which are however not selected according to any evident logic» [16, p. 151]. Moreover, Messiaen stated that it is mathematically impossible to find others. However, [24] and, later, [23] showed that there is one more, that had been intuitively used by Franz Liszt, Rimsky-Korsakov and Béla Bartók in their music. Actually, to unmistakably prove that there are no more than eight modes with limited transpositions is an issue of mathematical nature. This begs the question: would it have made any difference in Messiaen’s music? Although it is difficult to answer such a question², perhaps the discovery of the missing mode could have triggered some inspiration to Messiaen, or at the very least to other composers who read his composition treatise. Mathematics could have helped him/them in offering a complete taxonomy of the aforesaid modes.

Figure 1. The seven Messiaen’s *modes à transpositions limitées* and, in the end, the omitted one.

In fact, mathematics offers a reliable tool to answer questions on musical elements, such as for instance and above all the basic issues of properly defining, counting and eventually order them under meaningful principles. Its capabilities as a unique tool for deepening and understanding the underlying structures of several musical elements and techniques have been then proven by the numerous results achieved in the mathematical literature. Therefore, mathematics and mathematical

2 After all, it could be truly argued that the beauty of Messiaen’s scores and their aesthetics may remain untouched. In addition, the declared spirituality of his music might find a new meaning in the human limits of the tools of the composer himself.

theory are a valuable option for gaining musical knowledge. However, they are not only a tool for taxonomical discoveries. The meticulous study of the mathematical structures and combinatorial mechanisms that a specific set of musical objects hides let unlock differently hidden features of its expressive potential. It is a framework for potential artistic discoveries, as it will be shown in the following chapters.

2. The Reason for Music: Mathematics for Shaping Musical Elements

Composers face very often practical issues and questions in dealing with the musical materials that can find a powerful tool to solve and answer them in mathematics: as Iannis Xenakis claimed, so as to make an «effort to reduce certain sound sensations, to understand their logical causes, to dominate them, and then to use them in wanted construction» [26, p. ix]. Xenakis, for instance, relied mostly on the mathematics of stochastic processes and extensively described his techniques in [26].

To provide another example of the application potential of mathematics as a means for shaping musical elements, a technique developed by the Author will be offered that has been formally introduced in [7] and discussed from an aesthetic point view in [1] and [2]. The main issue was to find a way to deal with triads overcoming their most conventional use. In particular, the idea was to find complete sequences of triads through all the twenty-four major and minor ones in which 1) each major and minor triad is used only once and 2) the transformations involved are such as to move only one of the three notes of the triad to produce the new one. These sequences «are exclusively triadic and overall completely chromatic, since every pitch class appears exactly six times. So these classes of harmonic cycles can be a useful compositional device to define harmonic structures that are triadic (and in some cases locally diatonic) but without any tonal center» [1]. To check their existence and then to find, enumerate and classify them is a problem of mathematical nature – more specifically in the framework of graph theory, algebra and theory of computation – that has been solved in [7]. The sixty-two possible sequences have been found and grouped in eight cyclical models of transformations through their representations as specific paths on a graph introduced in [10], the so-called *chicken wire to-*

rus, that depicts triads as vertices and connects them with an edge if there exist a transformation for which they share two pitch classes out of three.

In this context, there is a vast array of possibilities that mathematics offers in shaping musical elements for the composition practice: the Author himself, for instance, has used the statistic methods of stylometry as a means to trace idiomatic playable patterns and to generate original ones for composing new music for guitar [3], or mathematical concepts and techniques taken from combinatorics and probability to define composing systems for non-musicians and discuss their aesthetics [4], just to name a few.

3. The Music of Reason: Mathematics for Triggering New Musical Ideas

Mathematics can even be a source by itself for triggering new musical ideas, without departing from music in order to head towards abstraction – and eventually and hopefully to come back to music, as it was described in the first two chapters – but rather beginning directly with the abstract realm of mathematics in order to head towards music. In fact, mathematics offers a unique ontology for representing, modeling, formalizing and visualizing musical objects which *per se* can be a huge field of inspiration.

A good example is given by the music and statements of the American composer Tom Johnson, who wrote: «I too like to find music that exists outside myself, rather than to compose something that is inside myself, but I am looking more in the direction of mathematical models. When I work with a logical sequence of numbers, or a set of permutations, or Pascal's triangle, or a logical sequence of geometric turns, or with the paper-folding formula, I have the feeling that I am working with absolutes» [14, p. 3]. He continues: «I can say, however, that there is something particularly satisfying about projects where the logic (the music) seems to arise naturally from some discovery outside of myself, and where everything comes together with a minimum of tampering (of composing)» [14, p. 6]. Not only the compositional attitude of Johnson offers an example of how mathematics has been used for triggering new music, but it also offers an example of a mathematically informed aesthetics, a topic that will be discussed in chapter four.

Therefore, mathematics can also be a device that let rethink music itself, which enters the cre-

ative process and the artistic compositional practice not only as a technical tool, but rather as an actual musical instrument to play with. It can be totally embedded in the artistic practice. Furthermore, mathematical activities are by themselves often considered a creative process.³ As Paul Lockhart wrote, «mathematics is the music of reason. To do mathematics is to engage in an act of discovery and conjecture, intuition and inspiration; to be in a state of confusion – not because it makes no sense to you, but because you gave it sense and you still don't understand what your creation is up to; to have a break-through idea; to be frustrated as an artist; to be awed and overwhelmed by an almost painful beauty» [15, p. 37].

Moreover, written music is given in a symbolic way, and a performance itself or an electronic composition may always be seen from the point of view of a spectrum and waveform of mathematical representation. It is quite natural then to find patterns in it, to get involved in its structural side outlining its organization, formal coherence and organicity. And thus to get captivated by the charming beauty of such an organization, which can be represented by means of mathematical tools⁴. So why not try to reverse the process and start with something which is purposely coherent, organized and organic? Which discipline can be more suited than mathematics – that can be seen as symbolic logic [19] and as the classification and study of all possible patterns [20] – in doing so?

4. Musicae Universales: Mathematically Informed Aesthetics of Composition

The ancient relation between music and mathematics briefly mentioned in the introduction is the reason of the presence of mathematics in the aesthetics of different historical music periods and composers. However, for the purposes of the present paper, only some recent examples from the beginning of the twentieth century onwards will be offered.

Joseph Schillinger, for instance, elaborated in the first half of the twentieth century a detailed system of musical composition – and even of the arts in general – founded on mathematical concepts, [21, 22]. The aesthetic assumptions he considered, mixing philosophical, scientific and

³ See also [25].

⁴ It is worth mentioning that chaotic forms can also be represented and obtained by means of mathematical tools.

artistic terminologies and frameworks, are hereby summarized. First and foremost, he stated that «if art implies selectivity, skill and organization, ascertainable principles must underlie it. Once such principles are discovered and formulated, works of art may be produced by scientific synthesis» [21, p. 3]. He continues arguing that «an esthetic reality may be either a natural product, a product of human creative intuition, or a product of scientific synthesis, realized through computation by mathematical logic» [21, p. 5]. Moreover, «everything that moves is a mechanism, and the science of motion is mechanics. The art of making music consists in arranging the motion of sounds [...] in such a manner that they appear to be organic, alive. The science of making music becomes thus the mechanics of musical sounds» [21, p. 5]. «Thus, analysis of esthetic form requires mathematical techniques» [21, p. 6]. In [22] he defined then a vast and comprehensive attempt to mathematically encompass all the elements and processes involved in music composition.

Schillinger's ideas are linked to a quantitative, technocratic approach to the creative process that can be found in many aesthetics and discourses on art. For instance, Austrian-born art historian Ernst Gombrich wrote, showing apparently a similar attitude and yet starting from the far context of Freud's aesthetics⁵, that «there must be (and there are) procedures in science and engineering where some medium or model is used for trying out structures through analogies and where techniques of systematic variation and permutation are used to discover fresh possibilities» [13, p. 38].

Moreover, notable composers derived their aesthetics and techniques also from the fascination of mathematics in a less systematic manner. Messiaen's idea of *impossibility*, that governs also his modes with limited transpositions introduced in the first chapter, or Arvo Pärt's *tintinnabuli*, rooted in strict rules [18], are just two of the several examples that can be provided.

5. Conclusions

Clearly, mathematics is not a necessary requirement – and certainly not a sufficient one for granting some sort of artistic quality or relevance – in the variety of skills, tools and knowledge of

⁵ A discourse on the combinatorial side of art embraced and continued by Italo Calvino in his lecture/essay *Cibernetica e fantasmî (Appunti sulla narrativa come processo combinatorio)*, [9].

a composer. However, it has been shown how, in the context of specific aims, mathematics can be a useful and reliable option that can lead to unique findings, outputs and aesthetics at different levels: from helping to study and understand musical elements, to assisting to shape them; from being an autonomous place of inspiration for triggering new ideas on music and to deal with its elements, to be put as the foundation of new aesthetics.

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